

Paper Electrophoresis in the Separation of—Ous and—Ic States of Copper

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PAPER electrophoresis was employed for the separation of ferrous and ferric ions by Lederer¹, who took ferro and ferricyanides in 0.5 N HCl carrier electrolyte. The migration of the same was observed by Lederer and Ward² in 1M KCl. Bigli and Trabanelli³ reported the separation of ferrous-dipyridyl, ferric and ferrous ions. Bigli, Trabanelli and Panacaldi¹ separated ferrous dipyridyl and ferric acetylacetonate complexes using Sodium potassium tartarate as carrier electrolyte.

In our previous communication*, electrophoretic separation of ferrous and ferric states have been reported. The present communication deals with the electrophoretic separation of cuprous and cupric states. Simple cations of Cu(I) and Cu(II) could not be separated by paper electrophoresis and therefore suitable complexes of Cu(I) as well as Cu(II) were prepared prior to electrophoresis. The stabilities of these cuprous and cupric complexes were ascertained by electrophorising them in different carrier electrolytes of varied concentrations. Only those electrolytes were selected for the separation of binary mixtures of cationic and anionic complexes of Cu(I) and Cu(II) in which both the species remained undecomposed. The choice of ligands was made in such a way so that complexes of opposite charges were obtained for cuprous and cupric states. Thus the difference in the direction of migration of the complexes caused the separation of ous and ic states of copper.

Experimental :

Two complexes of Cu(II) were cupric-EDTA ([Cu-EDTA]⁻²) and copper ethylenediamine ([Cu en₂]⁻²). Blue coloured anionic cupric E.D.T.A.

complex was prepared by heating freshly precipitated cupric oxide with 0.05M disodium salt of E. D. T. A. Cationic deep blue coloured ([Cu en₂]⁺²) complex was prepared by treating cupric salt solution with ethylene diamine. On the other hand ligands used to prepare cuprous complexes were thiourea and KCN. Cationic Cu(I) thiourea complex was prepared by treating freshly prepared Cu₂ Cl₂ with an aqueous solution of thiourea (tu) while the anionic Cu(I) complex was obtained by the addition of KCN solution to a cupric salt solution.

These complexes were electrophorised singly in different carrier electrolytes. Electrophoretic migration revealed that all the four complexes were stable in the electrolytes, viz. 0.1N NH₄Cl, 0.05M Na₂ E.D.T.A. and 0.1N NaF. Cu(I) thiourea and Cu E.D.T.A. complexes were found to be stable also in 0.002N HCl and 0.025M tartaric acid.

After ascertaining the stability of the complexes, the binary mixtures of cationic and anionic complexes were subjected to electrophoresis under the influence of potential gradient 5.88 volts per cm for a period of 2hrs. The electropherogram on development with rubeanic acid solution showed two well separated zones, one at the cathode corresponding to cationic complex and the other at the anode corresponding to the anionic complex.

Electrophoresis was conducted in Wieland and Fischer⁵ type horizontal electrophoretic set, using Whatman No. 1 paper strips as supporting medium of dimension 34 cms x 1 cm.

A table is given below showing the sequences of separation of complex ions where the "+" sign indicates the migration towards the anode, "-" sign towards the cathode and ":" sign point of application of the migrants. The complexes are represented in the table as [Cutu]⁺, [Cu en₂]⁻², [Cu(CN)₄]⁻³ and [Cu EDTA]⁻².

TABLE—1. SEPARATION OF CUPROUS & CUPRIC COMPLEXES.
Potential gradient = 5.88 Volts per cm. Time of run = 2 hrs
Dimension of paper strip = 34 cms x 1 cm

Composition of Cu(I)/Sequences of separation Cu(II) complex mixtures	Sequences of separation & distance of migration of migrants from the point of application.		Carrier electro- lyte
	"-"	"+"	
1. [Cutu] ⁺ & [Cu EDTA] ⁻²	[Cutu] ⁺ 1.5 cm	: [Cu EDTA] ⁻² 2.4 cms	0.05 M Na ₂ EDTA
2. [Cu en ₂] ⁺² & [Cu(CN) ₄] ⁻³	[Cu en ₂] ⁺² 2.6 cms	: [Cu(CN) ₄] ⁻³ 6.6 cms	- do -
3. [Cutu] ⁺ & [Cu EDTA] ⁻²	[Cutu] ⁺ 1.4 cm	: [Cu EDTA] ⁻² 2.7 cms	0.1 N NaF
4. [Cu en ₂] ⁺² & [Cu(CN) ₄] ⁻³	[Cu en ₂] ⁺² 4.8 cms	: [Cu(CN) ₄] ⁻³ 7 cms	- do -
5. [Cutu] ⁺ & [Cu EDTA] ⁻²	[Cutu] ⁺ 1.4 cms	: [Cu EDTA] ⁻² 2.9 cms	0.1N NH ₄ Cl
6. [Cu en ₂] ⁺² & [Cu(CN) ₄] ⁻³	[Cu en ₂] ⁺² 3.5 cms	: [Cu(CN) ₄] ⁻³ 4.4 cms	- do -
7. [Cutu] ⁺ & [Cu EDTA] ⁻²	[Cutu] ⁺ 2.2 cms	: [Cu EDTA] ⁻² 2.8 cms	0.002N HCl
8. [Cutu] ⁺ & [Cu EDTA] ⁻²	[Cutu] ⁺ 4.8 cms	: [Cu EDTA] ⁻² 2.7 cms	0.025M Tartaric acid

*H. G. MUKHERJEE and S. P. NAG, Proceedings of the 58th session of the Science Congress, 1971, 115,

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Polarography of Tin(II) in Lactic Acid Media

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THE literature on the polarographic behaviour of tin (II) in a medium composed of organic acids is scanty. The available references are of Deford¹ and co-workers¹, and Lingane². However, no reference has been found regarding the polarographic study of Sn(II) in lactic acid medium. Polarographic behaviour of tin(II) at dropping mercury electrode using lactic acid as a supporting electrolyte has been investigated in some detail. Tin (II) produces well-defined diffusion controlled irreversible double waves, one anodic and the other cathodic, with $E_{1/2}$ -0.16V and -0.49V (vs SCE) respectively in 0.5M lactic acid (pH~2.1). The effects of variation of pH, Hg-pressure and concentration on the wave have been studied.

All the chemicals used were either E. Merck's guaranteed reagent or BDH reagent grade. Tin content in stannous chloride solution was checked by the classical method³. Gelatin (0.01%) was used as a maximum suppressor.

Polarograms were recorded with a Leeds Northrup Electrochemograph type E. The non-polarizable reference electrode used was a saturated calomel electrode with Agar-KNO₃ bridge. The drop time was maintained at 3.2 sec with the open circuit and the product $m^{2/3}t^{1/6}$ was 2.098 mg^{2/3}/sec^{1/6}. Damping was kept constantly at 2 and recorder sensitivity at 50 x. The pH of the solutions were measured with a line operated Beckman Zeromatic pH meter. The pH of 0.5M lactic acid solution is 2.1; the pH being varied by means of dilute ammonium hydroxide. All experiments were performed at 25° ± 1°. Thoroughly mixed solution (20 ml) of supporting electrolyte, metal ion solution and gelatin was transferred to 50 ml pyrex beaker and was deoxygenated by pure nitrogen before recording the polarogram.

Tin (II) gives well-defined irreversible double waves, one anodic and the other cathodic with half-wave potentials -0.16V and -0.49V (vs SCE) respectively in 0.5M lactic acid. The cathodic and anodic diffusion currents are approximately equal and it is evident that the cathodic wave results from the reduction of the

stannous-lactate complex to the metal and the anodic wave corresponds to the oxidation of stannous-lactate complex to a stannic-lactate complex. These observations are in close agreement with that of Deford¹ and Lingane². Variation of pH and base electrolyte concentration did not affect the nature of the polarogram and a negative shift in $E_{1/2}$ was observed. Plots of $\log i/i_a - i$ Vs $E_{1/2}$ are linear but the resulting slopes were not found to be in agreement with theoretical values indicating the irreversible nature of the electrode reaction at dropping mercury electrode.

A number of polarograms in 0.5M lactic acid (pH ~2.1) with different concentrations of tin (II) were drawn. The diffusion current was measured by extrapolation method. The graph plotted between concentration of tin(II) and the diffusion current gave a straight line and can be used for quantitative estimation of tin. The plot of i_d vs square root of the height of the mercury reservoir was found to be linear and passes through the origin. This proves further the diffusion controlled nature of the wave. The diffusion current constant (I) for the anodic and cathodic wave was calculated from the well-known Ilkovic equation $I = i_d / cm^{2/3}t^{1/6}$ and found to be 2.774 and 2.819 respectively.

For determining the tin content of an unknown solution, its polarogram was recorded under the above-mentioned conditions and the diffusion current thus measured referred to the calibration curve obtained under identical operative conditions. The results are given in Table 1.

TABLE I—DETERMINATION OF TIN(II) IN LACTIC ACID MEDIA

Base electrolyte concn = 0.5M lactic acid + 0.01% gelatin, pH ~ 2.1. Total volume of the solution = 20ml			
Sl. No.	Amount of Sn(II) taken mg	Amount of Sn(II) found mg	Error mg
1.	1.18	1.06	-0.12
2.	0.94	0.94	—
3.	2.37	2.31	-0.06
4.	1.78	1.77	-0.01
5.	2.96	2.91	-0.05

It is apparent that tin (II) produces a well-defined irreversible double wave polarogram in lactic acid medium the height of which varies linearly with tin (II) concentration; the wave can be successfully utilized for the determination of tin.

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